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Abstract	Internal project communication is developed to consolidate a guidance for internal communication as a necessary step for a clear procedure on how the information is distributed within BLUE4ALL project. It includes internal communication procedures, internal adherence to the key deadlines and quality standards, quality reviews and describes how documents are being shared including a joint work on the deliverables in the consortium. A dedicated internal communication system was established (Microsoft SharePoint integrated with Teams) to ensure that all the partners are timely updated, the effective online discussion is ongoing, and data is shared timely across the partnership. These guidelines should facilitate the communication and organization of regular meetings to ensure cross-fertilization between the different Living Labs and WPs, and that the information and lessons learnt at each of the sites are transmitted in a timely fashion. It represents the project Deliverable 7.2 developed in the context of Task 7.4.
Keywords	Internal Communication, Cross-fertilization, Governance, SharePoint

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Acronyms

Advisory Board (AB)

Coordination Team (CT)

Deliverable (D)

Ethics Advisory Board (EAB)

European Commission (EC)

European Union (EU)

General Assembly (GA)

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Horizon Europe (HEU)

Intellectual Property (IP)

Lead Partner (LP)

M (Milestone)

Project Officer (PO)

Project Partner (PP)

Task (T)

Work Package (WP)

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable D7.2 refers to outputs of the task 7.4: Internal communication and cross-fertilization and to Deliverable 7.4: BLUE4ALL project governance structure which has been set under Task 7.1: Project management: BLUE4ALL Coordination Team. The connection between these tasks and deliverables is strong as communication flow is critical for effective collaboration within the consortium. It operates both as bottom-up and top-down and employs the typical communication methods such as: online and in person meetings, e-mail, as well as Microsoft SharePoint and Microsoft Teams online system for sharing information within the consortium and collaboration (hereafter referred to as SharePoint and Teams respectively). The SharePoint platform has been established before the official start of the project, while the interface with Teams was set following the Kick-off meeting to set a fully functional internal communication system. The SharePoint system is organized with a structure which enables all participants to upload and download information to and from the shared online document repository, to edit and work on the shared documents, while Teams has been integrated to allow cooperation among PPs through chats and online meetings. Minutes of meetings and project deliverables as well as templates and guidelines are made available to consortium partners through the SharePoint.

The aim of this deliverable is therefore to consolidate a guidance for internal communication as a necessary step for a clear procedure on how the information is distributed within BLUE4ALL project and that this procedure is adopted among Project Partners.

In addition, internal communication also includes a dedicated internal newsletter which will be useful to inform the PPs about key updates and project progress, deadlines, events, and news relevant to the partnership and will be released monthly. It also involves cross-fertilization and defines development of internal meetings and workshops, ensuring the most inclusive and integrated approaches are used (among Living Labs, Information sites and WPs), and proper links are established with the Advisory Board (as in T7.3), Mission Ocean, Prep4Blue project, as well as the other relevant projects and initiatives (as in T6.5).

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2. Introduction

The communication flow in the BLUE4ALL Consortium is envisaged to be bottom-up and top-down through the typical communication methods such as: meetings (physical and online) and e-mail, but also a cooperative working method using Microsoft SharePoint and Teams, which have been integrated in the BLUE4ALL internal communication system. This shared system is organized with a structure in which all participants can upload and download information to and from the different WPs and tasks according to their role and responsibilities, to edit and work on the shared documents, as well as to cooperate through chats and online meetings. Minutes and guidelines will be also made available through this internal communication system.

3. Internal Communication in the Consortium: vision and goals

The internal communications will be carried out between the members of the consortium, essential to ensure a proper project implementation. The main responsible for the definition of the communication procedures is SUBMARINER Network, in collaboration with the Lead Partner, and all the other PPs.

The internal organization and management of information flow ensures the efficient implementation of actions and information transfer, engagement within the BLUE4ALL community.

What are the goals of internal communication?

- Increase involvement and engagement among BLUE4ALL actors;
- keep PPs connected and informed;
- build ownership and share a common understanding of BLUE4ALL goals, vision and mission;
- develop a sense of community between PPs;
- raise awareness of the ongoing/future activities within the partnership;
- ensure sustainability of the project.

4. Communication Flow within the Consortium: methods and tools

The communication flow among the partners will use two main communication channels, email and an integrated system consisted of Microsoft SharePoint and Teams, in addition to physical meetings and internal newsletter. The guidelines for ensuring communication flow are necessary to provide the environment for collaboration among the partners in the consortium, through the established methods and tools. The centric project management team will ensure an efficient, fluent and controlled communication among all PPs during the project life.

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4.1 Internal Microsoft SharePoint

A private internal repository using the Microsoft SharePoint platform (Figure 1) has been established for the project. This internal platform has been setup and is used to share preliminary results and internal documents (e.g. working papers, deliverables progress, contacts, calendar of events, etc) among the project partners, jointly develop or comment upon documents directly online. SharePoint makes data accessible on all devices for users with access granted by RBINS. The system is organized with a structure in which all participants can upload and download information in an organised manner – categorizing information according to Work package and task. It should be used as follows:

8. Each Work Package has a dedicated folder in which the partners can upload documents and structure file storage for minutes, deliverable development, presentations, etc.
8. It is advised to keep developing deliverables in the SharePoint so that all partners can see the deliverables being developed and to minimize the number of word document iterations that occur sending deliverables back and for over e-mail.

The BLUE4ALL SharePoint has the following structure (Figure 1):

- 1) A repository named 'General' containing all general documents related to project, from project official documents (project development, application, consortium agreement etc), reviews, meetings documents and templates, to final submitted project deliverables. This repository also contains folders per each WP;
- 2) A repository structured per each WP (1-7), including deliverables, meetings and notes, reports, etc.

All the WP leads are invited to actively use their WP repositories, create and structure their folders and actively use Teams for the exchange with their group, joint work on the deliverables, etc.

Internal news and announcements will be sent by email and uploaded in the SharePoint to be sure to capture the group at large.

4.2 Internal Teams platform

Microsoft Teams is to be used as the board for discussion via chat or calls, and especially to hold WP/Task meetings. It is suggested to share upcoming meetings on the Teams so those who are not directly in the smaller e-mail groups now can also see the WP and Project meeting and join in out of interest and relevance.

BLUE4ALL Teams is structured in a way to ensure a dedicated channel per each WP, as well as for the Coordination Team, while additional channels can be created for Living Labs, information sites etc, upon request to be submitted to the Lead Partner (LP), RBINS and SUBMARINER

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Network. A channel named “General” will allow to all the PPs to share news, publications documents, examples of reports etc. BLUE4ALL Teams structure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 BLUE4ALL Microsoft SharePoint platform

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Figure 2 BLUE4ALL Teams platform

Most important guidelines and highlights on how to use Microsoft SharePoint and Teams and important information on their integration are provided in Annex I.

4.3 Email communication

In addition to the internal communication system, which was established to ease the number of e-mails and centralize the documents and presentation being developed, several group e-mailing lists have been created to facilitate communication that needs to take place outside of Teams. In the email communications, it is suggested to always start the subject field with 'BLUE4ALL' (e.g. e-mail subject: BLUE4ALL_First WP6 meeting announcement).

The already created email groups are the following:

- BLUE4ALLWPLoad@naturalsciences.be
Includes WP leads members (Coordination Team)
- BlueParks@naturalsciences.be
Includes all partners (Parties)
- BLUE4ALLAdvisoryBoard@naturalsciences.be
Includes all Advisory Board members

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To add an email to one of these groups, it is necessary to send a request to the emails: brumes@naturalsciences.be and lvigin@naturalsciences.be, as to ensure that all RBINS team members receive communications.

4.4 BLUE4ALL meetings

A series of regular conference calls are put in place to continually assess project status including risk management as well as planning next steps. Specifically, the Project Management Team consists of the Scientific (RBINS) and the Operational (SUB) Manager who are responsible for the overall project coordination. A BLUE4ALL Coordination Team (CT) as the project's governing body comprising all WP leads speaks at least once per month to monitor overall progress and processes as well as assess potential risks, challenges and mitigation measures if required. Focused groups inside the WPs, convene regularly to work on tasks together and update each other on progress as well as potential challenges. Notes from CT meetings including agreed action items are shared and agreed, and results are followed by the project Management Team.

Coordination Team monthly meetings

CT virtual meetings via Teams will take place monthly and serve for following up on the overall progress in the project, discussing the cross-linkages between WPs and solving possible issues that arise from possible delays in one or more WPs and coordinate future steps, specifically with view to realizing the deliverables.

In order to increase the effectiveness of the meetings, the CT will underline issues for the Ethics Advisory Board to look into, consider and discuss.

Meeting minutes are taken and shared by LP via email and SharePoint with all CT members, highlighting 1) agreed action to be taken; 2) agreed/suggested deadline; 3) responsible partner.

General Assembly meetings

All Project partners' meetings, so called 'General Assembly' (GA), takes place at least once a year to discuss on the progress in the project implementation as reported by the Steering Committee, including possible concerns and the way forward, taking decisions on content, finances and intellectual property rights, evolution of the consortium and appointments of CT Members and AB Members.

Meeting minutes are taken and shared by RBINS via email and SharePoint with all project partners. GA meetings are planned as in-person events allowing for interactions and group work to take place. In case of travel restrictions for whatever reason, hybrid or fully online options will be considered.

Individual Work Package and Task meetings

Each WP lead should organise regular check in meetings e.g. once a month with partners working on that WP, and all different ongoing tasks of that WP, in order to ensure alignment, synergy and cross fertilization among them. Task leads may also want to organise smaller regular task group meetings on regular and *ad-hoc* basis.

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Setting the date via Doodle Poll (link) can be useful in order to ensure coordination of schedules and proper participation of WP/task leads.

Meeting minutes should be taken and shared by WP/or task lead and shared with the respective group working on the given WP/task. It is strongly recommended that minutes are kept short and to the point highlighting the following three elements 1) agreed action to be taken; 2) agreed/suggested deadline; 3) responsible partner/person.

Communication with the European Commission Project Officer responsible for the BLUE4ALL

The BLUE4ALL lead partner, RBINS, specifically the project's overall coordinator is facilitating all the communication with the European Commission Project Officer (PO). Any financial, legal, administrative, and content related issues in the project should be timely communicated to the lead partner, which will contact the PO to communicate and discuss the matter. Partners should not attempt to contact the PO individually.

Advisory Board meetings

The project Advisory Board (AB) was established to build upon the existing knowledge and wider expertise. Their meetings will be chaired by the LP and aligned with the General Assembly meetings to present and discuss BLUE4ALL project to date progress. Meetings can be organized also on an *ad-hoc* basis, in line with identified needs.

Ethics Advisory Board meetings

The Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) was established early in the project, involving partners and some AB members to ensure consistent application of the legal and ethical frameworks references in the project Strategy for Addressing the Ethics and IP in the Project (D7.1).

When necessary, CT meetings will involve an agenda point related to the possible ethics issues – so the EAB meeting takes place as soon as any ethical or IPR related question arises. CT points out with which of the EAB members the matter should be discussed.

Logistical aspects of meetings organization

Recording of meetings

If the meeting is to be audio and/or visually recorded for reporting purposes – all partners should be informed about it orally at the start of the meeting and given the opportunity to object. In case of objections the recording should not take place.

Photographs/video of meetings

If photographs or videos are taken during the BLUE4ALL meetings, all partners should be informed that such material will be used in BLUE4ALL publications or other media material produced, such as brochures, invitations, books, newspapers, magazines, television, project website and others, without written permission of those included within the photograph/video. In case of objections the use/dissemination of such materials should not take place.

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4.5 Internal BLUE4ALL newsletter

SUBMARINER Network, as the leader of the WP6, will coordinate the internal newsletter of the project. A mailing template will be designed for this purpose.

Description of the Newsletter:

- While the sections of this publication are still to be determined, it will be fully nourished by updates on the progress of BLUE4ALL activities and news in that regard.
- The sender will always be an official account of the project, a representative of WP6.
- The language of the newsletter will be English.

Survey for collecting internal and external news

A jotform survey¹ will be sent out to all partners at least every two months (two weeks before the above mentioned internal newsletter is released) which serves to collect information on events that have been attended by a partner, other communication activities undertaken by a partner, future events known to the partner relevant to the BLUE4ALL project, and collect any other news and information relevant to the project and its partners (e.g. announcement about the progress of the task, information about relevant policy changes locally or at the EU level, grants or other opportunities). The information collected via the jot form survey will feed into the internal and external newsletter.

6. Internal governance structure and responsibilities

The Governance structure of the Project Consortium is set in the Deliverable 7.4 BLUE4ALL project governance structure, comprising the following Consortium Bodies:

- The General Assembly
- The Coordination Team
- The Coordinator (Project Coordination – Management Team)
- The Advisory Board (AB) which will validate the applicability of the project outcomes to achieving the EU Mission

The establishment of governance structure takes place during the kick-off phase of the project (as in M.1.1), as shown in Figure 3. It entails sound legal, contractual, financial and administrative management of the project, in compliance with the contractual obligations, good management practices and the provisions of the Consortium Agreement and release of end reports. The project management is facilitated by Teams, an online management system serving as an online repository for internal documents with individual access rights.

¹ Jotform is used for form building. It is an online web form builder in which you can create surveys, forms, reports. <https://www.jotform.com/answers/2219931-what-is-jotform-for-and-why-do-i-need-it>

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6.1 General Assembly

The General Assembly, as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium is chaired by the coordinator and comprising representatives from all partner institutes, will be responsible for the strategic decisions throughout the project. Major emphasis will be on the evaluation of progress made and planning for future work. The General Assembly physically met at the start of the project (kick-off meeting) and further on a yearly basis (four meetings in total). The latter will comprise a BLUE4ALL debriefing and legacy meeting at the end of the project, with emphasis on maximizing the uptake of the project outcomes within the EU MISSION on “Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030”.

6.2 Coordination Team (CT)

The Coordination Team (CT), which involves all WP leads/co-leads led by the LP is the project governing body which assures strategic guidance and is responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly. All risks and issues will be considered by the CT as part of the proper monitoring of the effective and efficient implementation of the Project and overall effectiveness of the project in terms of budget and adherence to deadlines, among others. SC shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.

6.3 Project Coordination - Project Management Team

The Project Management Team consists of the Scientific (RBINS) and the Operational (SUB) Manager who are responsible for the overall project coordination. The quality assurance and risk management sit under this task led by the Project Coordinator (RBINS). The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement and assure strategic guidance, and effective internal communication within the Consortium and the European Commission. The coordinator will chair the CT and will – together with the CT – align the communication with the EC project officer.

6.4 Advisory Board

The project Advisory Board was established during the kick-off phase of the project to build upon the existing knowledge and wider expertise, involving representatives from organizations with a direct link to the project. The membership of the Advisory Board was decided to span expertise about socio-ecology and governance of MPA (networks) from a scientific perspective as well as operational perspective, representing each European sea-basin involved in the project. The Advisory Board will be continuously engaged to validate the applicability of the project actions and outcomes to achieving the EU MISSION on “Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030”. Advisory Board led by the LP and SUBMARINER Network will discuss project issues of joint interest, identify new products (e.g. tools, models, data) and services that bring added value and can be further taken up by the relevant public and private decision makers.

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Figure 3 BLUE4ALL Governance Structure

7. Quality assurance, risk management and BLUE4ALL materials (documents, presentations, deliverables, etc.)

7.1 Quality assurance and risk management

The quality assurance and risk management sit under this task led by the assigned lead partner's Project Coordinator. The Consortium involves a project partner specialized and responsible for data management – VLIZ which will assign the BLUE4ALL Data Management Officer and also be supported, especially in terms of quality assurance, by data officers from relevant project partners. The project management is facilitated by Microsoft SharePoint, a secure management system serving as an online repository for internal documents with individual access rights.

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7.2 Working internal templates

Another important asset in terms of communication activity within the project is to have homogeneous formats related to project deliverables, documents, presentations or any other item eventually produced.

For this purpose, CMCC will produce different templates available for BLUE4ALL partners for main formats: .docx (for documents and deliverables), .pptx (for BLUE4ALL presentations).

7.3 Procedure for review of BLUE4ALL deliverables

Final deliverables should be submitted to the LP and assigned internal reviewers no later than one month before the contractual deliverable deadline. Two internal reviewers have been assigned for each deliverable, from project partners' representatives, on a voluntary basis or assigned by the LP. Upon the receipt of the deliverable, the reviewers and the lead partner have 14 days to review the deliverable. Upon the receipt of comments, the partner responsible for the deliverable has 14 days to finalise the deliverable and submit the final version to the LP. Lead partner uploads all the final deliverables to the European Commission portal, thus making it available to the PO and external reviewers assigned by the PO.

7.4 Ethics Advisory Board

The Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) was established in the kick-off phase of the project involving PPs and some of the AB members to ensure consistent application of legal and ethical frameworks (based on EC Ethics Appraisal Procedure) and assist the partnership in the appropriate implementation of activities and the monitoring of ethics aspects including the 'do no significant harm' principle and Intellectual Property (IP) rights protection, in line with the Strategy for Addressing the Ethics and IP in the Project (D7.1). A document outlining the strategy for addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project was developed in the first month of the project and will be updated regularly. The EAB will specifically review documents, tasks and deliverables mentioned in this strategy.

BLUE4ALL established a repository, Microsoft SharePoint, with individual access rights ensuring clear responsibilities for handling and protection of personal data and adherence to GDPR and other relevant laws. An Informed Consent form was developed and will be used to inform and obtain consent of each person participating in the project stakeholder activities and each person whose personal data is to be collected in the project (i.e. in case of interviews, interactive events, recorded trainings and webinars, surveys).

8. Other – guidance on how to be clear in your communication

- **EU interinstitutional style guide**
<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-000100.htm>

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- **Misused English words and Expressions in EU publications**
http://ec.europa.eu/translation/english/guidelines/documents/misused_english_terminology_eu_publications_en.pdf
- **How to write clearly**
<http://bookshop.europa.eu/en/how-to-write-clearly-pbHC3010536/>

9. Cross-fertilization inside and outside the project

In the Task 7.4 it is envisaged that throughout the project life regular meetings will be organized to facilitate the cross-fertilization between the different Living Labs and WPs, as an important part of project successful presentation and therefore internal communication. In addition to the internal meetings and workshops, ensuring the most inclusive and integrated approaches are used, proper external links will be established with the Advisory Board (T7.3). SUBMARINER Network will also ensure cross-linkages with similar projects and initiatives through its network, in particular in the of the Mission Ocean coordination activities, but also all other relevant and interlinked projects and initiatives.

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Annex I:

What is Microsoft SharePoint and how it can be used?²

In short, it's an online collaboration system that helps business teams work together. It allows organizations to create intranets, where they can store, organize and share business information on a centralized, protected platform through a web browser. In addition, to file sharing and file storing, it also provides stronger control over information access and helps them automate workflow. It's important to look at SharePoint as a platform rather than a single tool, as it enables many different activities.

More information at: <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/get-started-with-sharepoint-909ec2f0-05c8-4e92-8ad3-3f8b0b6cf261>

About Teams: how to use it and for what purpose?³

Creating folders and storing documents

Use the **Files** tab in Microsoft Teams to store and manage documents in the context of a record on a SharePoint Server. Documents are stored on a SharePoint Server that allows a user on Microsoft Teams to access the documents on the SharePoint Server – as long as the user has appropriate permissions.

A user's access to files in Microsoft Teams or customer engagement apps depends on their access to the SharePoint site the file is stored in.

Files that you upload to a channel are stored in your team's SharePoint folder. These files are available in the Files tab at the top of each channel.

Files that you upload to a one-on-one or group chat are stored in your OneDrive for Business folder and are shared only with the people in that conversation. These are available in the **Files** tab at the top of a chat.

Working jointly on deliverables

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dQVzxFh9yBc>

Chatting and video calling – individually and as a group

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y7HXc3yWAlk>

It is possible to make one-on-one or group calls with anyone in Teams directly from a chat without having to host a team meeting. These calls are private and won't appear in any team conversation. Entries for the calls will appear in the chat.

² <https://www.incworx.com/blog/how-to-use-sharepoint>

³ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoftteams/platform/>

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Steps:

Go to your **chat list**, and click **New chat** New chat button to start a new conversation.

Type the name or names into the **To** field at the top of your new chat.

Select **Video call** button or **Audio call** button to start a call.

Up to 20 people can be on the same video call. If a group chat includes more than 20 people, calling buttons will be disabled.

If you're not currently in a chat with the person you want to call, you can start a new call from a command. Go to the command box at the top of your screen and type /call, then type or select the name of the person you want to reach.

You can also start a one-on-one call from someone's profile card. Open it by clicking their picture in a channel or from a search.

Help section of the Teams

In the **Help** section of the BLUE4ALL Teams platform it is possible to find in the Trainings subsection videos and texts on the basic characteristics and opportunities of the platform, on how to work with posts and messages, how to upload, share and find files, manage chats, calls and meetings.

For some of the basic questions on how to use Teams you can find useful information and tutorials as provided in the links bellow:

What is Microsoft Teams?

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jugBQqE_2sM&list=PLXPr7gfUMmKxiPKpMocZRkA-AUDi9N1RB

How to create a folder in Teams?

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-WRByHIP49M>

How to upload a document in Teams?

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lufKJi3gLNc>

How to call someone in Teams?

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4OEEocWXFU>

Teams How To's

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<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ykymIT5IL5E&list=PLXPr7gfUMmKzwFu2OKzlwuCfhBlv6KCJG>